

EFFECT OF IAA ON THE PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF *Catharanthus roseus* (L.)G. DON

S. Muthulakshmi* & V. Pandiyarajan**

* Department of Botany With Specialization in Plant Biotechnology, The Standard Fireworks Rajaratnam College for Women (Autonomous), Sivakasi, Tamilnadu

** Centre for Research and Postgraduate Studies in Botany, Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal College (Autonomous With CPE Status), Sivakasi, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: S. Muthulakshmi & V. Pandiyarajan, "Effect of IAA on the Phytochemical Constituents of *Catharanthus roseus* (L.)G. Don", *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, Volume 1, Issue 1, Page Number 229-231, 2016

Abstract:

Catharanthus roseus (L.)G. Don is an important anticancerous plant belonging to the family Apocyanaceae. This plant may be considered as a famous chemical factory for biosynthesis of a huge array of phytochemical constituents and many of these chemicals are utilized as medicines. The effect of IAA on phytochemical content of *Catharanthus roseus* was studied. IAA was applied as foliar spray at different concentrations viz 50, 100, 150, and 200ppm for 30days. The phytochemical constituents were significantly maximum at 150 and 200ppm concentration of IAA when compared to other concentrations and control. Hence it is concluded that practice of application of IAA to *Catharanthus roseus* can be recommended for attaining better biomass production.

Key Words: Alkaloid, Foliar Spray, IAA & Phytochemical Constituents.

Introduction:

The medicinal plants are useful for healing as well as for curing of human diseases because of the presence of phytochemical constituents (Nostro *et al.*, 2000). Phytochemicals are naturally occurring in the medicinal plants, leaves, vegetables and roots that have defense mechanism and protect from various diseases. Phytochemicals are primary and secondary compounds. Chlorophyll, proteins and common sugars are included in primary constituents and secondary compounds have terpenoid, alkaloids and phenolic compounds (Krishnaiah *et al.*, 2007). Terpenoids exhibit various important pharmacological activities i.e., anti-inflammatory, anticancer, anti-malarial, inhibition of cholesterol synthesis, anti-viral and anti-bacterial activities (Mahato and Sen 1997). Terpenoids are very important in attracting useful mites and consume the herbivorous insects (Kappers *et al.*, 2005). Alkaloids are used as anaesthetic agents and are found in medicinal Plants (Hérouart *et al.*, 1998). *Catharanthus roseus* (L.) G. Don (Apocynaceae) derives its economic importance from its highly valued anticancer alkaloids vincristine and vinblastine, and its antihypertensive root alkaloid ajmalicine (Jaleel *et al.*, 2007). All parts of the plants are rich in alkaloids, with maximum concentrations found in the root All parts of the plant are credited with hypoglycaemic properties and are used to treat diabetes (Jaleel *et al.*, 2006). Thus it is over all a miracle plant which is having the more number of alkaloids used in pharmaceutical industries. (Edeoga and Eriata 2001). The main objective of our research work was to analyze the presence or absence of different phytochemicals in the selected medicinal plants.

Materials and Methods:

Cultivation of Plants:

The seeds of *Catharanthus roseus* were collected from the local stores, Sivakasi. The seeds were surface sterilized in 0.2% MgCl₂ solution for 5 minutes and pots were filled with a soil mixture containing red soil, sand and farm yard manure (1:1:1 ratio). The seeds were soaked in running water for 12-18 hours and allowed to germinate in pots.

Foliar Application of IAA:

Indole - 3 Acetic Acid was initially dissolved in 100 ml of ethanol and a stock solution of 5 mM was made up with distilled water containing 0.02% Tween-20 (Polyoxyethylene sorbitan). Selected concentrations viz., 50, 100, 150, and 200ppm were prepared. After 6 months the leaves were sprayed with different concentration of IAA (50, 100, 150, and 200ppm) using sprayer for a continuous period of 30 days care was taken to wet both the surfaces completely to ensure maximum application. The control plants were sprayed with distilled water. The phytochemical parameters were analysed after 30 days treatment of various concentrations of IAA.

Results and Discussion:

Growth promoting hormones have obviously been used owing to their beneficial effects on growth and yield of plants. Plants are completely dependent on hormonal co-ordination mechanism. Hormones occur in traces and are constantly maintained at low levels. Growth hormones are chemical messengers, which direct cell to carryout various functions of growth and differentiation.

In this study has revealed the presence of phytochemicals constituents considered as active components for medicine. Thus important phytochemicals constituents such as total alkaloids, Phenol, tannin, and saponin

were present in the samples. In our study the total alkaloid, tannin, and saponin content were increased under hormonal treatments showed in the Fig. 1.

Effect of IAA on Phytochemical Constituents:

IAA is believed to regulate plant physiological processes, because IAA can increase protein synthesis and regulation of enzyme activity. An increase in protein synthesis as raw material constituent enzymes in plant metabolic processes would enhance growth. This process can enhance the future growth which would increase the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites (Taiz and Zeiger 2006). The total alkaloid, tannin, saponin and vincristine content increased under hormonal treatment. But at high concentration an increase in the phenolic content was noticed. Borse and Dhumal (2001) observed that foliar application of IAA and GA₃ at different concentrations to *Solanum khasianum* enhanced the content of solasodine which supports our findings. IAA stimulated a considerable increase in alkaloids, saponins and tannins contents of *Balanites aegyptiaca* plants Araby *et al.* (2006). Alkaloid contents in the leaves of *Balanites aegyptiaca* plants were increased significantly by using different concentrations of IAA as compared with the control (Mostafa, *et al.*, 2011). Phyto regulators might modulate the expression of secondary compounds of a terpenic (Ortuno *et al.*, 1993) and alkaloid (Cho *et al.*, 1988). High concentration of IAA has brought about induction of alkaloids than the control.

High rates of Ethrel tended to increase total alkaloid with little effect on alkaloid profile. Ethrel treatment has produced similar effects in other studies with opium (Ramanathan 1978; Buzuk *et al.*, 2005). It has also increased alkaloid content in *Catharanthus roseus* (Pan *et al.*, 2010) and *Chrysanthemum cinerariaefolium* Vis. (Haque *et al.*, 2007). Which is consistent with the results of our present study. However, Ethrel also increased alkaloid content in young opium seedlings and is suggested to enhance translocation (Buzuk *et al.*, 2005) or increase flux of secondary metabolites (Haque *et al.*, 2007).

Figure 1: Typical changes in total alkaloids, phenols, saponin and tannin content of *Catharanthus* treated with various concentrations of IAA. The values are an average of 5 independent measurements. Mean \pm SE, n=5.

Conclusion:

The phytochemical analysis of the medicinal plants are also important and have commercial interest in both research institutes and pharmaceuticals companies for the manufacturing of the new drugs for treatment of various diseases. Thus we hope that the *Catharanthus* have important phytochemical properties.

Acknowledgement:

The authors are thankful to the Management and Principal for providing the necessary facilities to carry out the experiments.

References:

1. Araby, M.M., Mostafa, S.M.A., Ismail, A.I. and Hegazi, A.Z.A. 2006. Hormone and phenol levels during germination and osmopriming of tomato seeds and associated variations in portion patterns and anatomical seed features. *Acta Agron. Hungarica*. 54: 441-457.
2. Borse, S.G. and Dhumal, K.N. 2001. Use of plant growth regulators for improving growth and yield of *Solanum khasianum*. *J. medicinal and Aromatic Plants*. 22: 308-310.
3. Buzuk, G.N., Lovkova, M.Y. and Sokolova, S.M. 2005. Growth regulators and phytohormones in alkaloid production and accumulation in *Papaver somniferum* L. seedlings. *Doklady. Biol. Sci.* 405: 474-476.
4. Cho, G.H., Kim, D.I. and Pedersen, H. 1988. Ethephon enhancement of secondary metabolite synthesis in plant cell cultures. *Bio-technol. Prog.* 4: 184-188.
5. Edeoga H.O, Eriata D.O, 2001, *J. Med. Aromatic Plant Sci*, 23, 344,
6. Harborne, J.B. 1973. *Phytochemical methods. A guide to modern Techniques of plant Analysis.* Chapman and Hall, London. 267-270.
7. Hérouart D, Sangwan RS, Fliniaux MA, Sangwan-Norreel BS (1988) Variations in the Leaf Alkaloid Content of Androgenic Diploid Plants of *Datura innoxia*. *Planta Med* 54: 14-17.
8. Jaleel C.A., Gopi R, Sankar B, et al., 2007, *South Afri. J. Bot*, 73, 190.
9. Jaleel C.A., Gopi R, Alagu Lakshmanan G.M., Panneerselvam, R, 2006, *Plant. Sci*, 171, 271,
10. Kappers IF, Aharoni A, van Herpen TW, Luckerhoff LL, Dicke M, et al. (2005) Genetic engineering of terpenoid metabolism attracts bodyguards to *Arabidopsis*. *Science* 309: 2070-2072.
11. Krishnaiah D, Sarbatly R, Bono A (2007) Phytochemical antioxidants for health and medicine: A move towards nature. *Biotechnol Mol Biol Rev* 1: 97-104.
12. Mahato SB, Sen S (1997) Advances in triterpenoid research, 1990-1994. *Phytochemistry* 44: 1185-1236.
13. Mostafa, G.G. and Abou Alhand, M.F. 2011. Effect of gibberellic acid and indole 3-acetic acid on improving growth and accumulation of phytochemical composition in *Balanites aegyptiaca* plants. *Amer. J. Plant. Physiol.* 6: 36-43.
14. Nostro A, Germanò MP, D'angelo V, Marino A, Cannatelli MA (2000) Extraction methods and bioautography for evaluation of medicinal plant antimicrobial activity. *Lett Appl Microbiol* 30: 379-384.
15. Ortuno, A., Garcia Pugi, D., Sabater, F., Porrás, I., Ortuno Lidoan, A. and Del Rio, J. A. 1993. Influence of ethylene and ethephon on the sesquiterpene nootkatone production in *Citrus paradise*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 41: 1566-1569.
16. Pan, Q.F., Chen, Y., Wang, Q., Yuan, F., Xing, S.H., Tian, Y.S., Zhao, J.Y., Sun, X. F. and Tang, K.X. 2010. Effect of plant growth regulators on the biosynthesis of vinblastine, vindoline and catharanthine in *Catharanthus roseus*. *Plant Gr. Regul.* 60: 133-141.
17. Ramanathan, V.S. 1978. Effect of plant-growth regulators on the yield of opium and its morphine content in opium poppy. *Ind. J. Agric. Res.* 12: 246-250.
18. Singleton, V., Orthofer, R. and Lamuela-Raventos, R.M.. 1999. Analysis of total phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu reagent. *Methods Enzymol.* 99: 152-58.
19. Taiz L., Zeiger E. 2006. *Plant physiology*. 4th ed. Sinauer. Sunderland.
20. Van-Burden, T.P. and Robinson, W.C. 1981. Formation of complexes between protein and tannic acid *J. Agric. Food. Chemi.* 1: 77.